

Local Government in Croatia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Dario Runtic

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe
with the support of the Association of Cities in the Republic of Croatia

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Croatia: An Introduction

Dario Runtic, *NALAS Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Between the WWII and the Croatian independence, structure and number of subnational units changed frequently. A two-tier subnational government model dominated the era. The number of units varied from of 89 regional and 737 local governments in the 1950's down to 11 regional and 102 local government units during the last decade of the Socialistic Republic of Croatia.

The number of local governments increased significantly since the 1990's when Croatia declared its independence from former Yugoslavia. The 1992 Law on Territories of Counties, Cities and Municipalities laid out a new structure of subnational governments in the newly independent Republic of Croatia. Counties are regional governments, cities are urban local governments and municipalities are rural local governments. The 1992 Law established 20 counties, the City of Zagreb with dual city/county status, 68 cities and 405 municipalities. Over the course of years, fragmentation of local governments continued and currently rests at 20 regional, 555 local government units (127 cities and 428 municipalities) and the City of Zagreb with dual status.

The rationale for the 1992 fragmentation is frequently attributed to centralization of competencies and governance during war time. The legislative basis for such a territorial structure was established by the 1992 Law on Local Government and Administration. Both laws were published in the Official Gazette 90/1992 of December 30, 1992. The Law on Local Government and Administration stipulates that 'a municipality is a local government unit composed of several settlements which represents natural, economic and social unity interlinked with common interests of population', which basically provides grounds for broad fragmentation of the territory.

Both laws contain provisions related to voluntary amalgamation/border change and inter-municipal cooperation. The Law on Local Government and sectoral laws allow transfer of competencies between local, regional and even national authorities. Until 2015 the laws allowed representative bodies to change borders by mutual agreement of representative bodies and with prior consultation of citizens in case the border change affects inhabited settlement. Also, representative bodies or one third of the population can propose a change of territorial affiliation of the settlement or establishment of the new local government. As of 2015 the law was amended to provide for voluntary amalgamation of adjoining local governments. Representative bodies can decide to carry out amalgamation by majority vote of members of each representative body. Representative bodies are required to consult with the residents prior to a decision. Consultations are carried out under referenda rules and are obligatory for the representative body. There are no fiscal or other incentives for voluntary

amalgamation. So far there were no attempts at or cases of voluntary amalgamations of local governments. The lack of attempts at voluntary amalgamation could be attributed to the lack of external incentives and/or nationally driven initiatives for amalgamation. Limited resources coupled with the economies of scale should be one of the natural drives of change; however, major costs of public service provision (health, education, utilities) in lagging local governments are carried either by the regional government or neighboring local governments. Therefore, economies of scale do not seem to play a major role in voluntary amalgamation. External incentives may need to be used as a catalyst for voluntary amalgamation.

An alternative to amalgamation exists in a form of inter-municipal cooperation. Local governments are allowed to carry out their responsibilities through various forms of inter-municipal cooperation, be it joint administrative departments, companies or institutions. The Law on Local Government lays a broad foundation for voluntary inter-municipal cooperation and leaves it up to local governments to craft details of the cooperation through bi/multi-lateral agreements. There are no mandatory inter-municipal cooperation arrangements in provision of services. There are only a few examples of formal inter-municipal cooperation in Croatia and the subject area is not thoroughly researched. Therefore, the question remains why do local governments refrain from joint service delivery – be it lack of regulation, lack of incentives, political or other issues. In case of certain responsibilities that are provided by the regional government on behalf of smaller local governments (e.g. construction permitting), inter-municipal cooperation is limited because of legislative barriers. In case of some basic local government functions there may not be a sufficient economy of scale to encourage the change.

Joint local utility companies are a rather frequent form of service provision, although these are not considered voluntary cases of inter-municipal cooperation. These companies became 'joint' during the process of local government fragmentation in the 1990s – large local government were divided into several smaller local governments and each was given a share in the communal company. These companies primarily carry out water supply, wastewater and waste disposal services.

In terms of grassroots inter-municipal cooperation initiatives there are only a couple of examples in Croatia. One is the Kaštelir-Labinci, Sv. Lovreč and Vižinada joint Department for Finance and Legal Affairs in Istria. The other is a joint non-profit organization for international relations originally established by the municipalities of Tovarnik, Ilok, Nijemci, Tompojevci and Lovas.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 110/2015 on Territories of Counties, Cities and Municipalities

Law no 98/2019 on Local and Regional Self-Government

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Antic T and Ivanovic M, *Handbook for Inter-Municipal Cooperation* (Association of Municipalities 2011)

Pigey J H and Tomašević V, 'Inter-municipal Cooperation and Public Service Provision: International Practices, Case Studies in Croatia and Recommendations' (The Urban Institute/USAID 2006)

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